

Study of the ship resistance during swarm operation based on biomimetics

Jinhyeok Choi¹ and Gisu Song^{1*}

¹National Korea Maritime and Ocean University, Busan, South Korea

Abstract. In this study, the swarm operation of ships inspired by the natural behavior of a duck swarm is investigated through numerical simulation. The results show that swarm operation can be an alternative for reducing operating costs compared to operating individually. In nature, ducklings swim in positions where they experience less resistance by staying within the waves created by their mother. At these positions, ducklings experience reduced wave resistance and a wave riding effect. This allows ducklings to swim with less effort compared to swimming alone. In this study, this phenomenon was applied to ship operations. A KRISO Container Ship (KCS) and a fishing vessel in model scale were defined as a mother duck and a duckling, respectively. The simulation results showed that the fishing vessel experienced less resistance in all positions behind the KCS, and the amount of resistance reduction varied depending on the position. The best position for the fishing vessel is similar to where ducklings benefit most. When several fishing vessels were arranged like a group of ducks, the resistance reduction for the rear vessels became smaller but leveled out at a certain point. This study focuses on the hydrodynamic resistance performance of rear ships during swarm operation and also investigates the optimal swarm operation configurations.

Keywords: *Biomimetics, Swarm operation, Wave resistance, CFD, Duckling.*

1 Introduction

With the advent of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, technological trends in the marine transport industries and shipbuilding industries are rapidly developing. Among them, research related to autonomous and unmanned operation technologies that minimize accidents by human error and improve fuel efficiency is being actively conducted. As technologies for controlling such vessels developing, interest in controlling operating multiple ships as a swarm operation. Baek et al. [1] conducted a study on formation control techniques for autonomous navigation of unmanned surface vessels (USVs) based on potential fields. Operating multiple vessels in a swarm provides the advantage of performing missions more efficiently over a wider area compared to individual navigation. To maximize this advantage, studies have also been conducted on performing complex tasks that reflect dynamic, real-time environmental conditions. Kim et al. [2] developed small-scale USVs to verify swarm mission planning and autonomous navigation algorithms through real-sea experiments. And advanced control algorithms and navigation optimization technologies for the efficient operation of USV swarms are continuously being developed. To implement swarm navigation effectively, it is necessary not only to develop control technologies for multiple vessels, but also to understand the hydrodynamic interactions between each individual vessel in the swarm. Because each vessel in a swarm is exposed to a different hydrodynamic condition. Lee et al. [3] conducted numerical simulations with multiple vessels arranged in parallel. They confirmed that wave interference between ships in parallel formation causes changes in wave resistance depending on their distance and speed. Also, if multiple vessels are arranged longitudinally, the Kelvin wave generated by the leading vessel can affect the following vessels, such as their resistance characteristics. To maximize swarm navigation efficiency, it is essential to consider these hydrodynamic interactions when determining the optimal positions for trailing vessels, and to establish an optimal formation and spacing strategy accordingly. If the wave generated by the leading vessel is analyzed, the resistance of the following vessels can be reduced, thereby the overall energy consumption of the swarm can be minimized. In fact, the similar formation of vessel swarms is easily observed in nature, and this provide us valuable insights. For instance, the collective movement of birds and fish demonstrates the efficient formation.

* Correspondence to: gisu.song@kmou.ac.kr

The purpose of this study is to analyze the hydrodynamic resistance performance of vessels based on biomimetic approach. Among various examples in nature, ducks are known to form swarms on the free surface, similar to a ship. Yuan et al. [4] conducted a numerical study using velocity potential theory to investigate the resistance performance of ducklings following a mother duck. Inspired by this natural duck swarm, the ship swarm formation is mainly discussed in this study. We focused on how resistance changes according to the position of the rear ship and investigated the fundamental origin.

2 Numerical Method

2.1 Definition of target vessels

The ships used in this study are the KCS (KRISO Container Ship) and a fishing vessel on model scale. Main particulars and geometries are given in Table 1 and Fig. 1, respectively.

Figure 1. Geometry of the KCS and the fishing ship

Table 1. Main specifications of the KCS model and the fishing ship model

Item	KCS model (1/31.6)	The fishing ship model (1/5.35)
Length - L_{PP} [m]	7.2786	1.768
Beam - B_{WL} [m]	1.019	0.536
Depth - D [m]	0.6013	0.068
Draft - T [m]	0.3418	0.099
Displacement - Δ [m ³]	1.649	0.07
Speed - U [m/s]	2.196	2.446
Froude number	0.26	0.59

To simulate a group of ducks, it is necessary to consider vessels with Froude numbers representative of a mother duck and her ducklings. In a previous study [4], the Froude numbers of the mother duck and duckling were 0.25 and 0.5, respectively. Since the Froude number of the KCS is defined as 0.26, which is close to that of the mother duck, the mother duck can be represented by the KCS. For the duckling, a fishing vessel was chosen in this study. If the KCS were to be scaled to match the duckling's Froude number, the resulting Froude number would be 0.52. However, since the KCS was designed with a bulbous bow for a Froude number of about 0.26, it is not suitable for representing the ducklings. For this reason, rather than scaling the KCS to match the duckling's Froude number, it was necessary to select a vessel for which experimental data is available at a Froude number close to 0.5-0.6 to represent the duckling. In the case of fishing vessels, several benchmark datasets have been made publicly available. Another important consideration in selecting the vessel to simulate the duckling is its length. To effectively observe the wave-riding phenomenon, the length of the vessel representing the duckling must be shorter than the wavelength of the waves generated by the vessel representing the mother duck. The wavelength (λ) is defined by Equation (1), and the wavelength of the KCS is evaluated as 3.09 m at a Froude number of 0.26. As shown in Table 1, the length of the fishing vessel in model scale is less than the wavelength. For these reasons, a fishing vessel was chosen to represent the duckling in this study.

$$\lambda = 2\pi Fr^2 L_{PP} \quad (1)$$

As written above, this study was conducted in model scale, so the scale ratio of the KCS and the fishing vessel is different, respectively. This is because, in the process of selecting model ships that satisfy the Froude number and length conditions required to simulate a duck swarm, vessels with different scales were defined. Therefore, the length ratio between the KCS and the fishing vessel in full scale differs from that in model scale. As a result,

extrapolating the KCS and fishing vessel used in the simulations to full-scale ships would lead to a situation that different from the actual duck swarm. Additionally, as two different ships were used in this study, two characteristic lengths are involved. For consistency in data, all lengths shown in the following figures are based on the KCS model.

To simulate the formation of a mother and duckling, KCS and the fishing vessel were arranged longitudinally, resembling a duck swarm, and numerical simulations were performed. The spacing between the KCS and the fishing vessel was defined using the wavelength (λ) generated by the forward positioned KCS. A total of eight numerical simulations were conducted with intervals from 1.50λ to 3.25λ , increasing by 0.25λ each case.

The resistance reduction of the fishing vessel was represented using the C_{DR} , which indicates the difference in resistance compared to obtained value when the fishing vessel is sailing alone. C_{DR} is defined as in Equation (2), where R_S is the resistance of the fishing vessel when sailing alone, and R is the resistance when the fishing vessel is positioned in the swarm operation.

$$C_{DR} = \left(1 - \frac{R}{R_S}\right) \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

A negative C_{DR} value indicates that the resistance of the fishing vessel in the formation is larger than in the alone condition, while a positive C_{DR} indicates that the resistance has decreased compared with the alone condition. In other words, the larger the C_{DR} , the more the resistance is reduced compared to the alone condition.

2.2 Numerical set-up

Before simulating the duck swarm with KCS and fishing vessel, numerical simulations for each vessel were individually conducted to validate the numerical methodology through comparison with experimental data. The numerical simulations were carried out using the commercial CFD software, STAR-CCM+ ver. 16.06. The Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equation with RSM (Reynolds Stress Model) turbulence model [5] was applied. To realistically describe the ship waves generated by a ship, the volume of fluid (VOF) method was applied, furthermore, the overset-mesh method was applied to allow for heave and pitch motions of target vessels. The computational domain used in present simulations is shown in Fig. 2. Considering the calculation efficiency of numerical simulation, simulation was performed for the fluid domain that included only half of the hull. To reduce the computational time and cost, total simulations were performed on half-body condition of the target vessels. The size of the computational domain was normalized based on length of target vessel and defined as $2.5L_{PP}$ in the vertical direction, $7L_{PP}$ in the streamwise direction, and $2L_{PP}$ in the spanwise direction. Symmetry boundary conditions were applied left and right surfaces, velocity inlet boundary conditions were applied inlet, top and bottom surfaces, and pressure outlet boundary condition were applied outlet side.

Figure 2. Computational domain

The grid system for KCS used in this study is shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. As shown in Fig. 3, an unstructured grid system called by Trimmer type was applied. To reduce the total number of cells, the wall function was employed, and Y_1^+ was set to 50. Considering that the fishing vessel will be positioned behind the KCS during the duck swarm simulation, the wave resolving mesh was extended sufficiently far downstream from the KCS.

Figure 3. Grid system of the KCS

Table 2. Comparison of EFD and present simulation of the KCS

	EFD [5]	Present	Error [%]
$C_{TM,E+3}$	3.711	3.717	0.16
Trim [deg]	-0.169	-0.167	-1.40
Sinkage [m]	-0.0139	-0.0147	5.71

The experimental data used for comparing to numerical simulation is referred from the 2015 Tokyo CFD conference [6]. The comparison between the numerical simulation results and the experimental data at Froude number 0.26 is presented in Table 2. It was confirmed that there were no significant differences in resistance, trim and sinkage between the numerical simulation and experimental results.

In the duck swarm simulation, the fishing vessel is located on the wave generated by the KCS. Therefore, it is important that the wave pattern around the KCS is generated similarly to the experiment in numerical simulation. To verify this, the simulated wave profiles around the KCS were compared with experimental data. As shown in Fig. 4, the experimental value of the wave profiles generated by KCS was obtained from previous study [7] and there was no significant difference.

Figure 4. Wave pattern of the KCS

(a) $y/L_{PP} = 0.0741$

Figure 5. Longitudinal wave cuts

Figure 6. Wave profile on the KCS hull surface

For more strict validation, a comparison of the wave profiles was conducted. Fig. 5 shows the comparison of wave profiles from CFD simulation and experiment at some specified positions where y/L_{PP} is 0.0741, 0.1509, and 0.4224, respectively. The Y-axis and X-axis represents the normalized wave height the longitudinal position, respectively. Since the experimentally measured data exist only up to the position of $x/L_{PP} = 1.8$, it was not possible to compare all the values from the numerical simulation. As shown in Fig. 5, the wave profiles from the simulation are closely predicted to those of the measured data. Additionally, the wave profile on the KCS hull surface from the present simulation was also compared to experimental data in Fig. 6. Simulation results showed good agreement with measuring data. Based on numerical results compared above, it is confirm that the numerical set-up for KCS is reliable.

Next, the numerical method for the fishing vessel was also examined. The same numerical setup used for the KCS was equally applied. Similarly, the overset mesh method was employed for the fishing vessel to allow degrees of freedom in heave and pitch motions. The mesh around the fishing vessel was configured as shown in Fig. 7. The fishing vessel used in this study is the same geometry as that used in the experimental study by Park et al. [8] and the simulation results were compared with their experiment. As presented in Table 3, the resistance values showed minor differences. For the fishing vessel, comparison with model experiments was conducted at a speed of 2.446 m/s. However, when positioned behind the KCS, the fishing vessel must travel at the same speed as the KCS, 2.196 m/s. Therefore, an additional simulation was conducted, as a result, a resistance of 72.34 N was obtained. This value was used as the resistance of the fishing vessel in the standalone condition for the present study.

Figure 7. Grid system of the fishing vessel

Table 3. Comparison of EFD and present simulation of the fishing vessel

	EFD [7]	Present	Error [%]
R_{TM} [N]	80.97	80.66	-0.38

3 Results

3.1 Wake field analysis

Before consideration of KCS and the fishing vessel, the wake flow field behind the KCS alone was analyzed. Since previous study [4] was conducted by the potential simulation, the viscous effect could not be explained. Although this study was inspired by the duck formation in Yuan et al.'s study [4], the consideration of viscous effects is essential for the realistic analysis and understating of the flow field. The velocity normalized by ship speed behind the KCS is shown in Fig. 8. The wake region where the flow velocity is less than 95% of the KCS speed is clearly visualized. In other words, even the highest velocities in wake region are at least 5% slower than the ship speed of KCS. It was confirmed that the wake region extends longitudinally behind the KCS, and this is the area where the fishing vessel is located. Thus, even though ship speed of KCS and fishing vessel is same, the fishing vessel is exposed to lower actual inflow speed condition comparing to the operation alone condition and this situation significantly affects following vessel's resistance.

ssssss

Figure 8. Wake region downstream of the KCS

3.2 KCS & One fishing ship

The duckling effect was simulated by placing a fishing vessel in a straight line behind KCS at various intervals. The position of the fishing vessel was defined from 1.50λ to 3.25λ with 0.25λ intervals. Fig. 9 shows the wave patterns obtained from each simulation case, and it was observed that the wave pattern varies according to the fishing vessel's location.

Figure 9. Wave patterns of the KCS & the fishing vessel at each interval

1.5λ is defined as the base distance between the KCS and the fishing vessel. The height of the divergent waves generated by the fishing vessel at 1.75λ case is somewhat decreased comparing to base case. In case of 2.00λ , the transverse wave components were much diminished than those of base case. In case of 2.25λ , the divergent waves became amplified again. When the fishing vessel was located at 2.50λ , the overall wave distribution pattern is almost similar to those of 1.50λ case. The wave distributions behind fishing vessel in case of 2.75λ , 3.00λ , and 3.25λ were also almost same to those of 1.75λ , 2.00λ , and 2.25λ , respectively.

Figure 10. Wave profile of the KCS and C_{DR} of the fishing ship

This repeating tendency is directly related to reduction of the resistance on a fishing vessel. Fig. 10 shows the fluctuation of C_{DR} values along to distance from KCS. The starting point of x-axis ($x/L_{PP} = 0$) means the KCS's A.P. position. The C_{DR} variation exhibited a clear periodic pattern with respect to wavelength. These results indicate that when two vessels are aligned in a straight line, the absolute distance between them is very important on the resistance and wave pattern of the rear vessel. In other words, it depends on the position on the phase of the wave generated by the forward vessel. As the swarm's speed increases, the wavelength of the generated waves

also becomes longer as shown in Eq. (1). Consequently, the location at which the fishing vessel experiences minimum resistance shifts accordingly. To maintain optimal resistance reduction, the fishing vessel must adjust its distance from the KCS in response to change in wavelength.

The C_{DR} values for the fishing vessel were larger than zero ($C_{DR} > 0$) at all positions, it indicates that the resistance was lower than that of sailing alone situation. Even if the KCS and the fishing vessel travel at the same speed while maintaining a fixed distance, the flow velocity experienced by each vessel is actually different. Since the fishing vessel is positioned in a region with a slower velocity than the KCS's vessel speed, it experiences reduced resistance comparing to sailing alone at same speed. This confirms that the fishing vessel gains a resistance benefit simply by being positioned behind the KCS in resistance simulation.

From the KCS wave profile in Fig. 10, it can be observed that the wave amplitude decreases progressively downstream. As the wave amplitude decreases, the C_{DR} of the fishing vessel also tends to decrease further downstream. This is because the wave energy generated by the KCS decreases as it propagates downstream, leading to a reduction in wave amplitude. As a result, the interaction between the waves and the fishing vessel becomes weaker, which in turn reduces the resistance reduction effect obtained from the waves. According to Yuan et al.'s previous study [4], ducklings positioned behind the mother duck can even experience additional thrust, resulting in C_{DR} values exceeding 100%. However, in realistic simulation with two vessels of KCS and fishing vessel, such high C_{DR} values were not observed.

Among several simulation cases, the contradictory wave patterns with respect to two different positions, A and B in Fig. 10 were compared in Fig. 11. Position A and B represent the maximum and minimum C_{DR} position within one wavelength period. As wave elevation amplitude which is generated behind following vessel are smaller, the resistance of fishing vessel showed smaller resistance. Fig. 12 showed the wave amplitudes behind fishing vessel. In case of position A, it is relatively similar to that of isolation case. In contrast, the wave amplitude of position B is much less than that of isolation case. In case of position A, the bow of the fishing vessel is located at the wave crest generated by the KCS. At this point, the bow wave generated by the fishing vessel is superposed to the crest of the KCS generated wave, resulting amplified wave height. This amplification leads to larger waves around the fishing vessel and thus an increase in wave resistance. In contrast, at position B, the fishing vessel's bow wave superposition with the trough of the KCS generated wave, resulting wave damping. This leads to smaller waves around the vessel and reduces wave resistance. A ship's total resistance consists of viscous resistance and wave resistance. For the fishing vessel positioned behind the KCS, the viscous resistance is expected to be similar at both positions A and B, as the flow velocities experienced at both positions are comparable due to their location within the KCS wake. Therefore, the difference in total resistance between positions A and B is primarily attributed to the difference in wave resistance. By comparing the wave heights around and downstream of the fishing vessel at positions A and B in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, it was confirmed that the wave heights are smaller at position B where the resistance is significantly reduced indicating that the wave resistance of the fishing vessel is lowest at position B.

Figure 11. Wave patterns of the KCS & the fishing vessel at A and B

Figure 12. Wave profiles downstream of the fishing vessel at $y/L_{PP} = 0$

In previous study [4], the wave riding effect of a duckling was explained. When the duckling's chest is positioned at the wave trough and its body at the wave crest, its resistance is minimized. This is called by the wave riding effect. This phenomenon occurs when the wave increases the pressure on the duckling's abdomen, pushing it forward. At the same time, the low pressure on the duckling's chest is generated at the wave trough. Thus the pressure difference between the chest and abdomen of the duckling induces the pressure drag, resultantly.

Figure 13. Pressure distribution of the fishing vessel at positions A and B

Table 4. Comparison of trim and sinkage of the fishing vessel at positions A and B

	Fishing ship at position A	Fishing ship at position B
Trim [deg]	-0.564	0.046
Sinkage [m]	-0.017	-0.014

We would like to investigate whether the wave riding effect of duckling would be similarly repeated in the fishing vessel. To analyze clearly, the pressure distributions on fishing vessel at position A and B are given in Fig. 13. Based on the Fig. 13, it is clearly observed that higher pressure is distributed at the bow in case A comparing to that of case B. This is because the bow of the fishing vessel at position A is exposed to a wave crest. Conversely, higher pressure on stern in case B was simulated than that in case A. Through this comparison, it was confirmed that position B has a more advantageous pressure distribution for advance, with lower pressure at the bow and higher pressure at the stern comparing to those of position A. Additionally, this pressure distribution directly affects the trim of the fishing vessel. Table. 4 presents the trim and sinkage of the fishing vessel located in position A and B, respectively. A positive value indicates the bow trim and a negative value means the stern trim. In case of position A, the high pressure at the bow and low pressure at the stern led the stern trim. In case of position B,

the low pressure at the bow and high pressure at the stern induced to a bow trim. The sinkage at the two positions was expected to be similar. These results indicate that the wave riding effect is acting on the fishing vessel at position B, where a significant reduction in resistance was observed.

3.3 KCS & Three fishing ships

In real duck swarm, multiple ducklings follow a mother duck. In this section, the resistance of multiple fishing vessels positioned behind the KCS was analyzed to simulate similar situation. A total of three fishing vessels were placed behind the KCS in a row. As shown in Fig. 14, the distance between the KCS and the first following fishing vessel was set as 1.5λ and 2.0λ which is same as position A and B in Fig. 10 and defined as Case 1 and Case 2, respectively. The first fishing vessel is denoted as F.1, the second as F.2, and the third as F.3. In both cases (Case 1 and 2), the spacing between the fishing vessels was uniformly set as 2.0λ , that λ represents the wavelength generated by the KCS. In nature, ducklings instinctively position themselves where resistance is minimized, which corresponds to the pattern observed in Case 2. In contrast, Case 1 was intentionally designed to examine how resistance is affected when the vessels are positioned. The wave patterns in Case 1 and Case 2 are shown in Fig. 15 which indicates that that the wave amplitude generated around the fishing vessels in Case 2 is overall smaller than those of Case 1. Fig. 16 presents the KCS wave profile and the C_{DR} values for each fishing vessel in Case 1 and Case 2. In Case 1, the C_{DR} is increased progressively from F.1 to F.3, this indicates that the amount of resistance reduction is increased and converged for following vessels further downstream. In contrast, in Case 2, the C_{DR} is decreased from F.1 to F.3. This shows that the amount of resistance reduction is also decreased and converged for following vessels positioned farther downstream.

This trend is attributed to the fact that vessels positioned farther downstream are exposed to smaller waves, resulting in weaker interactions between the wave and the fishing vessel. Consequently, the differences in C_{DR} between Case 1 and Case 2 gradually diminish 18.58% for F.1, 5.92% for F.2, and 3.10% for F.3, respectively. Therefore, it can be predicted that if additional fishing vessels were placed behind F.3, the C_{DR} values may be converged but the resistance reduction effect is still expected.

Figure 14. Arrangement of the Case 1 and Case 2

Figure 15. Wave patterns of the Case 1 and Case 2

Figure 16. Wave profile of the KCS and C_{DR} of the Case 1 and Case 2

4 Conclusions

In this study, the investigation of the hydrodynamic resistance performance for a rear vessel during swarm operation is mainly examined. This topic is originated by the natural behavior of duck swarms. The swarm operation configuration was constructed by a KCS and fishing vessel which is chosen by the considering of Froude number. A model scale KCS with a similar Froude number was used to represent the mother duck, and a model scale fishing vessel was applied to represent the ducklings.

The numerical analysis clearly showed that the fishing vessels located behind the KCS were exposed to an actually slower inflow velocity due to the wake of the KCS. This leads the reduced resistance comparing to sailing a lone situation. However, depending on the location, the rate of reduction was different, and the tendency is similar to that of ducklings. It was also found that the resistance reduction effect diminished as the fishing vessel positioned farther downstream from the KCS. Through present study, it is confirmed that the key mechanisms of resistance reduction on a rear fishing vessel is the combination of wake effect and wave riding effect. This was confirmed through the analysis of wave patterns, pressure distributions, and the fishing vessel trim. Furthermore, when multiple fishing vessels were arranged behind the KCS, the resistance trends were examined, and the presence of the wave-passing phenomenon was also identified.

However, in this study, there is a limitation for the explaining of ducking effects by ship, because the propeller effect was not considered. In future works, the effect of self-propulsion effect will be studied and compared to those results from resistance simulations.

References

- [1] S.D. Baek, M.S. Kim and J.H. Woo. A formation control of swarm unmanned surface vehicles using potential field considering relative velocity. *Journal of the Society of Naval Architects of Korea*, Vol.61, pp.170-184, 2024
- [2] D.H. Kim and B.W. Choi. The development and experimentation of unmanned surface vehicles (USV) for swarm operation. *Journal of Institute of Control, Robotics and Systems*, 28(5):420-426, 2022
- [3] W.H. Lee and B.W. Nam. Numerical analysis of wave interference effects on ship resistance in parallel arrangements. *Journal of Ocean Engineering and Technology*, 38(6), 325-335, 2024
- [4] Z. Yuan, M. Chen, L. Jia, C. Ji and A. Incecik. Wave-riding and wave-passing by ducklings in formation swimming. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 928, R2, 2021.
- [5] A. Farkas, N. Degiuli, I. Martić and R. Dejhalla. Numerical and experimental assessment of nominal wake for a bulk carrier. *Journal of Marine Science and Technology*, 2018
- [6] https://t2015.nmri.go.jp/Instructions_KCS/Case_2.1/Case_2-1.html.
- [7] A. Yu, D. Wan and G. Chen. Verification and validation for the resistance of a KRISO container ship in calm water. *International Ocean and Polar Engineering Conference, Honolulu, Hawaii*, 2019
- [8] D.W. Park. An experimental study on the resistance performance of fishing vessel appendages. *Journal of the Korean Society of Marine Engineering*, Vol.42, pp.668-674, 2018